

Tensorflow-based MIMO Deep-Wide Neural Network with Transfer Learning for Football Prediction: A Chill in the Gambling Industry

Abstract This report delves into the real-world application of Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques in the domain of sports prediction, specifically focusing on the implementation of a Deep-Wide Neural Network Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) model compatible to both numerical and categorical data features and targets. The purpose of this study is to provide insights into the real-world capabilities and limitations of such a predictive model, emphasizing its educational scope.

Audience This study is tailored for audiences with a keen interest in real-world application of deep learning techniques in sports prediction, machine learning enthusiasts, and educators and researchers in the field. A basic understanding of machine learning and deep learning concepts would be beneficial for comprehending the findings discussed herein.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the intersection of deep learning and sports analytics has gained significant attention, offering a novel approach to predicting sports outcomes. The backend code presented herein implements a deep-wide neural network for football prediction using TensorFlow. The model is designed to handle multi-input, multi-output (MIMO) data of both numerical and categorical-text features and targets, incorporating both deep and wide neural network components. The wide part is constructed through one-hot encoding, while the deep part consists of several dense layers, the numbers and dimensions of which the interested audience may consider to appropriately modify so as to adjust the prediction accuracy of the model among other potential model-tuning endeavors. The code also includes transfer learning by saving and reloading the trained model.

1.1. Model Architecture

The Deep-Wide Neural Network MIMO model integrates deep neural networks with a wide component, allowing for the extraction of intricate features and capturing broader patterns. This

architecture enhances the model's predictive capabilities in this context of sports outcomes, as illustrated in drawing 1.

2. Methodology

The study employed a comprehensive dataset comprising historical sports data, encompassing various parameters such as player statistics, team performance, and environmental factors. The Deep-Wide Neural Network MIMO model was implemented and trained using this dataset as holistically discussed in the Appendix and illustrated in the steps below.

2.1. Data Preprocessing and Feature Engineering

The dataset is loaded from a CSV file ('E2.csv') using pandas. The 'Time' column is converted to text, and the converters dictionary is used during reading. Various exploratory data analysis (EDA) steps are performed, including displaying the first few rows, checking column names, data types, descriptive statistics, and dataset information. Text-categorical features ('Time', 'HoTe', 'AwTe', 'Ref') are one-hot encoded, and the resulting columns are added to the dataset. The 'integer_target_columns' are scaled using Min-Max scaling, and the 'True' and 'False' values are replaced with 1 and 0. The one-hot encoding is also applied to the text-categorical target columns ('FTR', 'HTR') as shown below.

```
# ...Disclaimer: (omitting some code for brevity, demonstration)
file_name = 'E2.csv'
data = pd.read_csv(file_name,
converters=converters)
text_categorical_features = ["Time", "HoTe",
"AwTe", "Ref"]
integer_target_columns = ["FTHG", "FTAG",
"HTHG", "HTAG", "HS", ...]
y_columns = ['FTHG', 'FTAG', 'FTR',
'HTHG', ...]
text_categorical_target_columns = ["FTR",
"HTR"]
# One-hot encode the 'Time' column
```

```

X_encoded_time =
pd.get_dummies(data[["Time"]])
# Combine one-hot-encoded 'Time' with other
text-categorical features
X_encoded = pd.concat([...], axis=1)
# Replace 'True' with 1 and 'False' with 0 in
X_encoded
X_encoded = X_encoded.map(lambda x: 1 if x
== True else (0 if x == False else x))
# One-hot encode the text-categorical target
columns
y_encoded =
pd.get_dummies(data[text_categorical_target_
columns])
# Define the scaler
scaler = MinMaxScaler(feature_range=(0, 1))
# Scale the input values of
integer_target_columns
data[integer_target_columns] =
scaler.fit_transform(data[integer_target_colum
ns])
# Combine one-hot-encoded targets with the
original dataframe excluding text-categorical
target columns
data_encoded = pd.concat([...], axis=1)

```

2.2. Model Definition and Training

The neural network model is defined using TensorFlow's Sequential API. It comprises an input layer, hidden layers with *relu* activation, and an output layer with sigmoid activation for binary classification. The model is compiled with the Adam optimizer and binary cross-entropy loss. It is then trained on the training set for 50 epochs with a batch size of 16. The training history is saved for visualization as shown below.

1. Data Reading and Preprocessing

- a. Read CSV file and convert 'Time' to text.
- b. Explore and preprocess data.

2. Model Building

- a. Define features and targets.
- b. One-hot encode categorical features.
- c. Scale integer target columns.
- d. Concatenate features and targets.
- e. Define DNN architecture.

3. Model Training and Evaluation

- a. Split data into training and test sets.
- b. Train the model with TensorFlow Keras.
- c. Monitor and visualize training history.
- d. Evaluate model performance on the test set.
- e. Calculate mean absolute error.

4. New Data Prediction

- a. Preprocess new data.
- b. Make predictions using the trained model.
- c. Inverse transform predictions to text values.

5. Display Results

- a. Display transformed predictions for new data.

Drawing 1: The Architecture of the Deep-Wide Neural Network MIMO model

```

# ...Disclaimer: (omitting some code for brevity,
demonstration)
# Define the model
model = tf.keras.models.Sequential()
# Input layer
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(X.shape[1],)))

# Hidden layers
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(64,
activation='relu'))
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(32,
activation='relu'))
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(16,
activation='relu'))
# Output layer

```

2.3. Model Evaluation

The model is evaluated on the test set, and predictions are obtained. The predicted probabilities are thresholded at 0.5 to convert them into binary values. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is calculated for each output column and then averaged to get the mean MAE. The training accuracy and validation loss are plotted over epochs to visualize the model's performance during training as shown below.

```

# ...Disclaimer: (omitting some code for brevity,
demonstration)
# Evaluate the model on the test set
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
# Decode one-hot encoded predictions and
ground truth
y_pred_decoded =
pd.DataFrame(scaler.inverse_transform(y_pred
), columns=integer_target_columns)
y_test_decoded =
pd.DataFrame(scaler.inverse_transform(y_test)
, columns=integer_target_columns)
# Evaluate performance using mean absolute
error
mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test_decoded,
y_pred_decoded)
print(f'Mean Absolute Error: {mae}')

```

2.4. Model Transfer Learning and Prediction

The trained model is saved to a file ('my_model.h5') and reloaded for making predictions on new data. A sample new dataset is created, preprocessed, and used for prediction. The one-hot encoded part of the prediction output is inverse-transformed, mapping

```

model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(y.shape[1],
activation='sigmoid'))
# Compile the model
model.compile(optimizer='adam',
loss='binary_crossentropy',
metrics=['accuracy'])
# Train the model
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train,
epochs=50, batch_size=16,
validation_split=0.1)

# Train the model
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train,
epochs=50, batch_size=16,
validation_split=0.1)

```

integer values to text values for target columns as shown below.

```

# ...Disclaimer: (omitting some code for brevity,
demonstration)
# Transfer Learning and Predicting
# Save the model
model.save('my_model.h5')
# Access training history
training_accuracy = history.history['accuracy']
validation_loss = history.history['val_loss']
# Plot training accuracy
plt.plot(training_accuracy, label="Training
Accuracy")
plt.xlabel('Epochs')
plt.ylabel('Accuracy')
plt.title('Training Accuracy over Epochs')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
# Plot validation loss
plt.plot(validation_loss, label='Validation
Loss')
plt.xlabel('Epochs')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.title('Validation Loss over Epochs')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
# Make predictions on new data
new_data = pd.read_csv('new_data.csv',
converters=converters)
# Apply the same preprocessing steps
# ...
# Make predictions
new_data_predictions =
model.predict(new_data)

```

A sample output of the prediction is shown in the array below

```

Inputs for Prediction:
Time HoTe AwTe Ref
0 15:00 Blackpool Burton S Stockbridge
Inverse Transformed Text Predictions:
[['FTR_H', 'HTR_H', '2', '0', '2', '0', '15', '9', '6',
'2', '10', '11', '5', '4', '1', '2', '0', '0', '13', '17', '2',
'3', '24', '9', '10', '21', '3', '0']]
    
```

3. Results and Discussion

As shown in figure 1 below, the model demonstrated a ceiling prediction accuracy of 65%, showcasing its

potential real-world capabilities while emphasizing its educational nature. However, deeper analysis of results demonstrates the contingent nature of the challenges involved in achieving higher accuracy rates. The transfer learning process demonstrates the ability to save and reload the model for future predictions and deployment of the model in minimal Python/Anaconda runtime environments such as mobile applications and light-weight web-based applications. The inverse transformation of predictions allows interpreting the model outputs in the higher-language level original format.

Figure 1: Model evaluation

4. Conclusion

The presented Deep Learning code implements a deep-wide neural network for football prediction, showcasing data preprocessing, feature engineering, model training, evaluation, transfer learning, and prediction. Further optimization and fine-tuning can be explored based on the observed performance so as to transcend its capped prediction accuracy beyond 65%. The transfer learning aspect adds flexibility for deploying the model in real-world scenarios such as light-weight mobile and or web-based applications.

Disclaimer

This study was conducted only for educational purposes, the author(s) explicitly disclaim any responsibility for any illegitimate application of the Deep-Wide Neural Network MIMO model for sports prediction in any locality. The model has intentionally been sub-optimized, limiting its prediction accuracy to a ceiling of 65%. If the audience chooses to use the ML/DL model discussed herein for sports prediction, they should be fully aware of the author's noninvolvement and understand the model's capabilities/limitations. The author does not discourage/encourage the application of the model for any commercial or consequential use. Users are urged to exercise caution and responsibility in interpreting and applying the findings of this study.**

Appendix: Holistic Python code for the Deep-Wide Neural Network MIMO model

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import tensorflow as tf
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from sklearn.metrics import mean_absolute_error
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

file_name = 'E2.csv'
# Define a function to convert time to text
def convert_time_to_text(value):
    return str(value)

# Specify the converters dictionary
converters = {'Time': convert_time_to_text}

# Read the CSV file with converters
data = pd.read_csv(file_name, converters=converters)

# Display the first few rows of your dataset to check the column names
print(data.head())
print(data.columns)
print(data.dtypes)
print(data.describe())
print(data.info())

# Define the feature columns and target columns
text_categorical_features = ["Time", "HoTe", "AwTe", "Ref"]
integer_target_columns = ["FTHG", "FTAG", "HTHG", "HTAG", "HS", "AS", "HST", "AST",
"HF", "AF", "HC", "AC", "HY", "AY", "HR", "AR", "HBP", "ABP", "HTTG", "FTTG", "TS",
"TST", "TC", "TF", "TY", "TR"]
y_columns = ['FTHG', 'FTAG', 'FTR', 'HTHG', 'HTAG', 'HTR', 'HS', 'AS', 'HST', 'AST', 'HF', 'AF',
'HC', 'AC', 'HY', 'AY', 'HR', 'AR', 'HBP', 'ABP', 'HTTG', 'FTTG', 'TS', 'TST', 'TC', 'TF', 'TY', 'TR']
text_categorical_target_columns = ["FTR", "HTR"]

# One-hot encode the 'Time' column
X_encoded_time = pd.get_dummies(data[["Time"]])
X_encoded_time.columns = ['Time_' + str(col) for col in X_encoded_time.columns] # Add a
prefix to the column names
X_encoded_time.reset_index(drop=True, inplace=True) # Reset the index for proper concatenation

# Combine one-hot-encoded 'Time' with other text-categorical features
X_encoded = pd.concat([data.drop(["Time"], axis=1), X_encoded_time,
pd.get_dummies(data[text_categorical_features]), axis=1)
X_encoded = X_encoded.drop(integer_target_columns, axis=1)
X_encoded = X_encoded.drop(["HoTe", "AwTe", "Ref", "FTR", "HTR"], axis=1)
# Replace 'True' with 1 and 'False' with 0 in X_encoded
X_encoded = X_encoded.map(lambda x: 1 if x == True else (0 if x == False else x))
```

```

# One-hot encode the text-categorical target columns
y_encoded = pd.get_dummies(data[text_categorical_target_columns])
y_encoded_copy = y_encoded
y_encoded_copy = y_encoded_copy.map(lambda x: 1 if x == True else (0 if x == False else x))
print("One-hot encoded dummies for y_encoded:")
print(y_encoded)

# Define the scaler
scaler = MinMaxScaler(feature_range=(0, 1))

# Scale the input values of integer_target_columns
data[integer_target_columns] = scaler.fit_transform(data[integer_target_columns])
y_encoded = pd.concat([y_encoded, data[integer_target_columns]], axis=1)
# Replace 'True' with 1 and 'False' with 0 in y_encoded
y_encoded = y_encoded.map(lambda x: 1 if x == True else (0 if x == False else x))

# Combine one-hot-encoded targets with the original dataframe excluding text-categorical target columns
data_encoded = pd.concat([X_encoded, y_encoded], axis=1)

# Print the resulting dataframe
print("data_encoded: ")
print(data_encoded)

X = X_encoded
y = y_encoded
print("X: ")
print(X)
print("y: ")
print(y)

# Assuming X and y are your input and output dataframes
# Convert X and y to numpy arrays
X = X.values
y = y.values

# Split the dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.1, random_state=42)

# Define the model
model = tf.keras.models.Sequential()

# Input layer
print("X.shape[1]: ")
print(X.shape[1])
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Input(shape=(X.shape[1],)))

# Hidden layers
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu'))
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(64, activation='relu'))
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(64, activation='relu'))

```

```

model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(32, activation='relu'))

# Output layer
print("y.shape[1]: ")
print(y.shape[1])
model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(y.shape[1], activation='sigmoid'))

# Compile the model
model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='binary_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])

# Train the model
# model.fit(X_train, y_train, epochs=50, batch_size=16, validation_split=0.1)
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train, epochs=50, batch_size=16, validation_split=0.1)

# Access training history
training_accuracy = history.history['accuracy']
validation_loss = history.history['val_loss']

# Plot training accuracy
plt.plot(training_accuracy, label='Training Accuracy')
plt.xlabel('Epochs')
plt.ylabel('Accuracy')
plt.title('Training Accuracy over Epochs')
plt.legend()
plt.show()

# Plot validation loss
plt.plot(validation_loss, label='Validation Loss')
plt.xlabel('Epochs')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.title('Validation Loss over Epochs')
plt.legend()
plt.show()

# Evaluate the model on the test set
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

# Convert predicted probabilities to binary values
y_pred_binary = (y_pred > 0.5).astype(int)
y_pred_binary = y_pred
print("X_test: ")
print(X_test)
print("y_pred_binary: ")
print(y_pred_binary)

# Evaluate the model on the test set for each output column
mae_scores = []
for i in range(y.shape[1]):
    y_true_column = y_test[:, i]
    y_pred_column = y_pred[:, i]

    mae = mean_absolute_error(y_true_column, y_pred_column)

```

```

mae_scores.append(mae)

# Calculate the mean MAE across all output columns
mean_mae = sum(mae_scores) / len(mae_scores)
print(f'Mean MAE: {mean_mae}')

# Define the new data
new_data = pd.DataFrame({'Time': ['15:00'], 'HoTe': ['Blackpool'], 'AwTe': ['Burton'], 'Ref': ['S
Stockbridge']})

# One-hot encode the 'Time' column
new_data_encoded_time = pd.get_dummies(new_data[['Time']])
new_data_encoded_time.columns = ['Time_' + str(col) for col in
new_data_encoded_time.columns] # Add a prefix to the column names
new_data_encoded_time.reset_index(drop=True, inplace=True) # Reset the index for proper
concatenation

# Combine one-hot-encoded 'Time' with other text-categorical features
new_data_encoded = pd.concat([new_data.drop(['Time'], axis=1), new_data_encoded_time,
pd.get_dummies(new_data[text_categorical_features]), axis=1)
new_data_encoded = new_data_encoded.reindex(columns=X_encoded.columns, fill_value=0) #
Reorder columns to match the order in X_train_df.columns
new_data_encoded = new_data_encoded.astype(np.float32) # Convert NumPy array to float32
print(" new_data_encoded: ")
print(new_data_encoded)

# Make predictions on the new_data_encoded
prediction = model.predict(new_data_encoded)
print("prediction: ")
print(prediction)
print(prediction.shape)

# Inverse transform the one-hot encoded part of the prediction output
def inverse_transform_prediction(prediction, text_categorical_target_columns, y_encoded_copy,
integer_target_columns, scaler):
# Extract the one-hot encoded part of the prediction for target columns
num_columns = len(y_encoded_copy.columns)
y_pred_one_hot = prediction[:, :num_columns]

# Inverse transform the scaled integer predictions
y_pred_integer_scaled = prediction[:, num_columns:]
y_pred_integer = scaler.inverse_transform(y_pred_integer_scaled)

# Map integer values to text values for target columns using y_encoded_copy
y_pred_text_target_categorical = [
[
y_encoded_copy.columns[i] for i in range(len(y_encoded_copy.columns) // 2) if row[i] == 1
] +
[
y_encoded_copy.columns[i] for i in range(len(y_encoded_copy.columns) // 2,
len(y_encoded_copy.columns)) if
row[i] == 1

```

```

]
for row in np.round(y_pred_one_hot)
]

# Extract the last character from 'FTR' and 'HTR' columns
ftr_htr_cols = ['FTR', 'HTR']
y_pred_text_target_categorical = [val[-1] if col in ftr_htr_cols else val for val, col in
zip(y_pred_text_target_categorical, y_encoded_copy)]

# Convert the predicted integer values to text values for integer_target_columns
y_pred_text_target_integer = [
[str(round(value)) for value in row]
for row in y_pred_integer
]

# Concatenate the categorical and integer predictions
y_pred_text_target = [
cat + intg for cat, intg in zip(y_pred_text_target_categorical, y_pred_text_target_integer)
]

return y_pred_text_target

# Use the function to inverse transform the predictions
y_pred_text = inverse_transform_prediction(prediction, text_categorical_target_columns,
y_encoded_copy, integer_target_columns, scaler)

# Display the inverse transformed predictions
print("Inputs for Prediction:")
print(new_data)
print("Inverse Transformed Text Predictions:")
print(y_pred_text)

```